

CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES IN INTEGRATING ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION FOR YOUTH DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract: Entrepreneurial creativity and innovation are key elements required for sustainability at all levels of development. These skills can be acquired either formally or informally; however, Entrepreneurship Education plays a critical role in successful enterprise creation. Enterprises established without adequate entrepreneurship education are more likely to fail due to poor preparation for business-related challenges, particularly in start-up phases.

This paper examines the effect of entrepreneurship education on youth development in Nigeria. The study is anchored on the Human Capital Theory as advocated by Robert (1991). Secondary data sources were primarily utilized for data collection. The objectives of the study were to investigate the challenges militating against the success of entrepreneurship education in Nigeria and to examine how entrepreneurship education can contribute to nation building.

The study concludes that through well-planned and effectively implemented entrepreneurship education, Nigerian youths can become more productive, fulfilled, and committed—either as employees or as employers of labour. This would enable them to utilize their unique capabilities toward achieving national and global development goals rather than seeking opportunities abroad.

The paper recommends that entrepreneurship education should be fully integrated into ongoing career preparation programs in secondary schools, colleges of education, polytechnics, and universities. It is imperative that the nation's workforce acquires entrepreneurial skills and attitudes before entering the labour market to compete effectively and efficiently in today's dynamic marketplace.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship Education; Youth Development; Human Capital Theory; Nation Building; Nigeria; Start-ups

Introduction

Nigeria is a country with numerous business and investment youths, and the increase in the number of those withdrawn potentials due to the abundant, vibrant and dynamic human from the workforce.

Youths havewell spring of ideas for and natural resources it possesses (Utomi, 2011).Although, it innovation which would spur economic, political and social is a nation blessed with numerous natural and material growth if harnessed. It is expected that

youths be gainfully resources but large proportion of the population live in abject engaged. However, unemployment has remained a perennial poverty as a result of unemployment problems. Nigeria is still problem that Nigerian youths have lived to battle with every one of the poorest countries in the world and has one of the day. Self-employment in small enterprises has been identified highest rates of youth unemployment in sub-Sahara Africa as a partial solution (Nelson, 1986; Republic of Kenya, Chukwubuike (2008). Youth unemployment is a critical 1992). Hopefully, entrepreneurship education can play a major problem in Nigeria and other African countries. The situation role in changing attitudes of young people and providing them of the Nigerian youths in the labour market has remained a with skills that will enable them to start and manage small worrisome development, as youth unemployment and job enterprises at some point in their lives (Oyelola O.T et al losses have become a national issue which the government of 2014). Many other countries have been able to energize and the day is yet to address. More worrisome is the poor working transform entrepreneurship sub-sector to such a vibrant one condition and the paltry remuneration of some employed that they have been able to reduce to the barest minimum their unemployment and poverty level because of the immense contribution of the sub-sector to their economic growth and development, but such cannot be said of Nigeria (Onugu, 2005). Research by White and Kenyon (2000) also found a 'flourishing youth enterprise culture' in the United Kingdom among young entrepreneurs aged 18-24 years. In Zambia, it was show that 25% of the youth are self-employed (Chigunta, 2001). Most

of these young people especially, younger youth, tend to be concentrated in marginal trading and service activities. Also, findings in Ghana of small scale enterprises reveal that young people owned almost 40 percent of the enterprises (Osei, Baah-Nuakoh, Tutu, and Sowa, 1993). Similarly, research in South Africa suggests that the probability of self-employment among young people rises with age (Chigunta, 2001). The study of entrepreneurship dates back to the work of Richard Cantillon and Adam Smith in the Late 17th and early 18th centuries, but was largely ignored theoretically until the late 19th and early 20th centuries. In the 20th century, the understanding of entrepreneurship owes much to the work of economist Joseph Schumpeter (1934) who advocated the theory of 'Creative Destruction' and other Austrian economists such as Carl Menger, Ludwig von Mises and Friedrich von Hayek, (Lucas 1978; Jovanovic 1982 in Anyadike et al 2012)). They noted that high youth unemployment in the society is associated with a low degree of entrepreneurial activities where people are not motivated to set up enterprises; then the rate of unemployment tends to be very high. The import of the above assertion is that those who are unemployed tend to remain so because they possess lower endowments of human capital and entrepreneurial talents required to set up new firms. A low rate of entrepreneurship culture and skills in any society may be a consequence of the low entrepreneurship education which reflects in higher levels of unemployment among youths (Audretsch, 1995, Oladele, P. O. et al, 2011). For Awogbenle and Iwuamadi (2010), the statistics from the Manpower Board and the National Bureau of Statistics showed that Nigeria has a youth population of 80 million,

representing 60% of the total population of the country, 64 million of them are unemployed, while 1.6 million are under-employed. According to National Bureau of Statistics (2009:238; 2010:2), the national unemployment rates for Nigeria between 2000 and 2009 showed that the number of unemployed persons constituted 31.1% in 2000; 13.6% in 2001; 12.6% in 2002; 14.8% in 2003; 13.4% in 2004; 11.9% in 2005; 13.7% in 2006; 14.6% in 2007; 14.9% in 2008 and 19.7% in 2009, 21.1 in 2010 and 23.9 in 2011. Youth unemployment is one of the principal social and economic challenges of this decade in Africa and around the world. Long spells of unemployment can have serious long-term negative effects on individuals, such as reduced earnings and social exclusion. The rate of youth unemployment in Nigeria is high, even at the period of economic normalcy i.e. the oil boom of the 1970s (6.2%); 1980s (9.8%) and the 1990s (11.5%) to 21.1% in 2010 and 24% in 2011 (NPC, CBN, McKinsey analysis, 2012). Besides, this has foisted a state of hopelessness on majority of young people who have resorted to crime, arm robbery, kidnapping, drug trafficking in order to make ends meet. They resorted to these vices because they are not gainfully employed. People especially youths and graduates became displaced economically (Kuratko, 2009), a situation that clearly negates the Millennium Development Goals for 2015. Without mincing words; it is evident that entrepreneurial skills are needed to tackle these menaces. This calls for serious training and re-orientation among our youths. Entrepreneurship education and training entails philosophy of self-reliance such as creating a new cultural and productive environment, promoting

new sets of attitudes and culture for the attainment of future challenges (Arogundade, 2011). The success of entrepreneur in business depends on many factors including training and education, but these are often negligible. Also, most of the government efforts to reduce poverty in the country were not tailored towards entrepreneurship education and organization of training for the unemployed people in the society. Entrepreneurial activities have been found to be capable of making positive impacts on the economy of a nation and the quality of life of the people (Adejumo, 2000). In fact, there are streams of benefits associated with entrepreneurship education such as poverty reduction, self-employment, self-reliance, self-confidence etc. Studies have attested to it by establishing its positive relationship with stimulation of economic growth; employment generation; and empowerment of the disadvantaged segment of the population, which include women and the poor (Oluremi and Gbenga, 2011; Thomas and Mueller, 2000; Reynolds, 1987).

The dexterity with which hunger and poverty have devastated lives and future ambition of youths especially graduates in Nigeria, have led to scholars advocating entrepreneurship education as the permanent cure for extreme hunger and poverty necessitated by unemployment. In the views of (Adebayo 1999; Alanana 2003; Echebiri 2005; Ayinde 2008), developing entrepreneurship has been identified as a means of providing employment and a powerful weapon of fighting poverty in the country. Entrepreneurship development is crucial in boosting productivity, increasing completion and innovation, creating employment and prosperity and revitalizing

economies. When Nigerians especially unemployed youth are mentored and provided with the needed resources and enabling environment for business startups, they will economically be engaged thereby shunning the illegal acts of hostage-taking, kidnapping, bombing, vandalism and homelessness. Ogundele (2007) suggested that the promotion and development of entrepreneurial activities would aid the dispersal and diversification of economic activities and induce even development in a country. Similarly, Osuagwu (2002) added that entrepreneurial development in Nigeria should be perceived as a catalyst to increase the rate of economic growth, create job opportunities, reduce import of manufactured goods and decrease the trade deficits that result from such imports. An entrepreneurship education remains the gateway to sustainable wealth creation in Nigeria (Ogundele, 2000). In the opinion of Matanmi and Awodun (2005), if Nigeria desire to move out of the disturbing high level of unemployment and ravaging level of poverty, adequate attention must be given to the growth of entrepreneurship. In Nigeria, most of the poverty alleviation measures or initiatives are embedded in entrepreneurship but have suffered several challenges culminating into their failure. Some of the schemes include National Poverty Alleviation Programme (NAPEP), Youth Empowerment Scheme (YES), Rural Infrastructural Development Scheme (RIDS), and Natural Resources Development and Conservation Scheme (NRDCS). It is against this background that this study was set out to determine the impact of entrepreneurship education on youth development in Nigeria.

Statement of the problem

The Nigerian youths are confronted with poverty, unemployment, urbanization, lack of capacity and skills needed to move the economy forward. This is because the youths are deficient in basic entrepreneurial and productive skills required to function effectively. Unemployment and poverty especially among the youths have remained major challenges threatening the economic growth and development of Nigeria. Statistically, Okafor (2011) cited a national survey jointly sponsored by National Universities Commission (NUC) and the Education Trust Fund (ETF) in 2004 sought to determine the labour market needs; revealed that 44 percent of the 20 organizations rated Nigerian science graduates as average in competence, 56 percent rated them as average in innovation, 50 percent rated them average in rational judgment, 63 percent as average in leadership skills and 44 percent as average in creativity. On needed skills like literacy, oral communication, information technology, entrepreneurship, analytical, problem solving and decision making, 60 percent rated them as poor. Thus, the above statistics showcase a poor assessment of Nigerian university graduates and further buttress the argument that Nigerian university graduates are unemployable (Okafor, 2011). These problems therefore demand that the youths be empowered with creative problem-solving skills. The training of educated individuals who can function effectively in the society for the betterment of self and the society will require special attention as the system will be deliberately set to concern itself with the development of sound human capital required for national development (Ocho, 2005). It is a clear-cut ideology

to state categorically that for any society to be regarded and recognized in the committee of developed countries, it must be entrepreneurship – oriented. In a bid to actualize this dream, entrepreneurship education becomes paramount in our society.

Objectives of the study

Under the auspices of the foregoing study, the following objectives are coined out to give credence to this work:

*To examine the effect of entrepreneurship education on youths development in Nigeria.

*To determine the challenges confronting entrepreneurship education in Nigeria

*To investigate the role of entrepreneurship education in nation building

Review of related literature

Conceptual review:

Entrepreneurship, according to (Ogundele 2000) is the process of emergence behaviour and performance of entrepreneur. Entrepreneurship education is a structured formal conveyance of entrepreneurial competencies, which in turn refers to the concepts, skills and mental awareness used by individuals during the process of starting and developing their growth oriented ventures. Another view of entrepreneurship education is the term given to someone who has innovative ideas and transforms them to profitable activities (Omolayo, 2006) Ogundele (2000 and 2005) defines entrepreneurship as the processes of emergence, behaviour and performance of entrepreneurs. The consortium for entrepreneurship education (2004) point out that entrepreneurship education is a life-long learning process and consist of five stages namely, basic,

competency awareness, creative application, start-up and growth as depicted.

Entrepreneurship Education is a carefully planned process that eventuates into the acquisition of entrepreneurial competencies. The education is a set of valuable skills needed by the entrepreneur to avoid future trials and errors (Osuala, 2004). By implications, the stage of learning is the stage to make mistakes and learn from them. Entrepreneurship education equips learners with skills in decision making, acquisition of new ideas, methods of initiating and maintaining conversations and establishing business relationships. Through entrepreneurship education, qualitative ability that facilitates computation of record-keeping are learnt (Alex.I.I 2012)

The term entrepreneurship education is used interchangeably with entrepreneurship training and skill acquisition. Conceptually, entrepreneurship education refers to a specialized knowledge that inculcates in learners the traits of risk-taking, innovation, arbitrage and co-ordination of factors of production for the purpose of creating new products or services for new and existing users within human communities (ACS and Storey 2004, Minniti and Lévesque 2008, Naudé 2007; Kanothi, 2009).

Mauchil et al., (2011:1307) assert that entrepreneurship education can be defined “as the process of providing individuals with the ability to recognize commercial opportunities and the knowledge, skills and attitudes to act on them. Entrepreneurship education has also been described as a formal or informal structured learning that inculcates in students/trainees the ability to identify, screen and seize available opportunities in the

environment in addition to skill acquisition (Sexton and Smilor, 1997; Jones and English (2004)).

In the words of Shane and Venkataraman (2000:218), the thrust of entrepreneurship training entails identifying “the sources of opportunities, the processes of discovery, evaluation, and exploitation of opportunities; and the set of individuals who discover, evaluate and exploit them.” The deliverables of entrepreneurship education when properly imbibed by students and learners are: ability to identify something happening in the environment (resources); and the ability to impart something new to trainees, so that their creativity, innovative abilities, beliefs and recombination skills would be enhanced (Sofoluwe, 2007; Fuduric, 2008). When the definition of OECD Entrepreneurship Indicator Programme is reshaped to fit into the present discourse, then entrepreneurship education can be described as a training that stimulates learners to better their lives by generating value through the creation or expansion of economic activity, identification and exploiting new products, processes or markets (OECD Entrepreneurship Indicator Programme, 2009). Anything that can be taught is education. Since entrepreneurship can be taught, entrepreneurship education refer to pragmatic and meaningful interaction between learner and instructor for the purpose of developing the ability of the learners to identify, evaluate and generate ideas and solve business problems in a unique way (Towobola and Raimi, 2011).

Entrepreneurship education when effectively and efficiently taught has the likelihood to precipitates self-employment among learners and accelerating sustainable growth and development. This is evident

in a number of developed nations like Japan and America that utilized entrepreneurial (facilitative) education for improving their human capital as opposed to the traditional approach of teach-and-listen approach, which is prevalent in the developing third world nation (Witte and Wolf, 2003; Raimi et al., 2011).

Besides, entrepreneurship education has also been viewed as a learning process that imbibes in the learners/students traits and competencies such as team spirit, leadership, problem solving, negotiation skills, self-direction and selfmanagement, unlike the traditional stereotype education, which places less attention on skills and practical needs of the world of work (Soskice, 1993; Sofoluwe, 2007; Gabadeen and Raimi, 2012). From several definitions provided above, entrepreneurship education can be conceptualized as a specialized and all-round training programme designed by education authorities to change the worldview of students from job seekers to wealth creators by developing their latent talents and potentials.

A youth is a young person especially a young man or boy; it refers to young people collectively.

It can be seen as the freshness and vitality characteristic of a young person (Word web Dictionary, 2010).

Development, on the other hand is a state in which things are improving. It also means ‘to Change gradually, progressing through a number of stages towards some sort of state of expansion, improvement or completeness or a state in which the subjects true identity is revealed (Word web Dictionary, 2010) . Indeed, youths are one of the greatest assets that any

nation can have and therefore, need to be developed and empowered.

According to Nigeria's National Youth Development Policy (2001), the youth comprises all young persons of ages 18 to 35, who are citizens of the Federal Republic of Nigeria. This category represents the most active, the most volatile and yet the most vulnerable segment of the population. They are individuals (male or female) above ten but below thirty years of age. Youth has also been defined as the period in an individual's life which runs between the end of childhood and entry into the world of work (Onuekwusi and Effiong, 2002). People in this age bracket definitely constitute a sizeable chunk of a nation's population on which the burden of national building falls. The youth also constitute the major resource base for any country that wants to embark on any meaningful development. Investment in the youth is the only way to ensure the future growth and development of any country since they are our potential and future leaders.

Studies carried out by (Fenley 1986; Odusanya 1972; and Olujide 1999) as cited in Emeh, Ikechukwu Eke Jeffry (2012) revealed that the youths constitute the highest percentage of the Nigerian population, and therefore are seen as "vital sources of manpower for development. They are rightly seen as potential leaders of tomorrow. Hence, the kind of education formal or informal that youths are exposed to or have access to will determine the nation's overall development (Odusanya, 1972, Olujide, 1999).

Theoretical review

Human Capital Theory: This theory is propounded by Robert (1991). It advocates education as a tool for improving human capital, stimulating labour

productivity and boasting the levels of technology across the globe. Human capital theorist encourages spending on nation's workforce because expenditure on training and development is a productive investment. Besides, human capital improvement through quality education is a critical factor that propels economic growth and development in East Africa, Hong Kong, Korea, Singapore and Taiwan.

MCCLELLANDS' ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION THEORY (1961):

According to McClelland, some people have need for achievement, some for power and others for affiliation. People with strong need for achievement tend to be highly motivated by challenging and competitive work situations. He asserts that a high need for achievement in a national population is necessary to launch and sustain a high level of economic development i.e there is a correlation between high achievement needs and high performance. The high achievement is linked with entrepreneurial spirit necessary to take some risks and develop a country's economic resources.

The import of this theory is that when youths are sufficiently motivated to have high need for achievement in life through entrepreneurship education, there is greater tendency for them to set up their own businesses after graduation without waiting for white collar jobs.

The new growth theory.

This prescribes knowledge and technical progress as main drivers of economic growth in any society. Economists concur that growth is essential for development, thus, knowledge put to productive use propels development. This implies that entrepreneurship education is sine qua non for

knowledge acquisition and technical progress of our young people. **This work is anchored on Human Capital Theory by Robert (1991).** This is supported by (Bryant, 2003; Ochu 2005) that stressed the importance of training sound human capital required for national growth and development.

Youth development through entrepreneurship education

The key roles of entrepreneurship include mobilization of domestic savings for investment, contribution to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and Gross National Income (GNI), harnessing of local raw materials, employment creation, poverty reduction and alleviation, enhancement in standard of living, increase in per capita income, skills acquisition, and advancement in technology and expert growth and diversification. Nigerian youths are confronted with myriads of problems ranging from poverty, unemployment, diseases, restiveness etc. This ugly situation calls for an urgent attention towards youth empowerment through various skills acquisition. For skills to be acquired, the training of youths who can function effectively in the society for the betterment of self in particular and society at large becomes a paramount issue. This is in sync with the views of (Byrant, 2003; Ochu 2005) that stressed the importance of training sound human capital required for national growth and development.

Entrepreneurship Education must be seen and utilized as a major contributor in the development process as well as a sharper of our youths since our future heavily depends on these young people. Also the opportunity and responsibility to transform our society into a healthy and productive economy relies on youths especially through the auspices of entrepreneurship.

Nigeria as a nation must ensure that schools where youths are taught are deliberately planned to provide sector-specific skills needed for the development of human capital. This could be achieved by establishing base of capital professionals and entrepreneurs who will act as instructors and mentors (Alek.I.I 2012).

Furthermore, there is need for re-orientation of teachers and lecturers in our various citadels of learning so that the method of teaching will be reflective of the fact that the goal of entrepreneurship is grooming of minds of students since entrepreneurship is primarily by experience and discovery. It has also been observed that the educational curriculum in Nigeria focuses more on the theoretical without a corresponding practical approach. Most employers are always compelled to retrain their employees due to lack of knowledge of basic work ideas or familiarity with the area of study of the employee (Anyadike et al, 2012).

The role of entrepreneurship education in nation building

Nigeria is naturally endowed with entrepreneurial opportunities; but the realization of full potential of these opportunities has been hampered by the adoption of inappropriate industrialization policies at various times. Entrepreneurial mind-set is prevalent in Yoruba land in Western Nigeria; Hausa land in Northern Nigeria and among the Igbo people in eastern Nigeria. (Remai, Shokunbi and Peluola 2010). Entrepreneurship education when effectively and efficiently taught has the likelihood to precipitate self-employment among learners and accelerating sustainable growth and development. This is evident in a number of developed nations like Japan and America that utilized entrepreneurial (facilitative)

education for improving their human capital as opposed to the traditional approach of teach-and-listen approach, which is prevalent in the developing third world nation (Witte and Wolf, 2003; Raimi et al., 2011). Nigeria adopted entrepreneurship education to accelerate economic growth and development.

The entrepreneur is the key player in the private sector of the economy and can be defined as an individual who scans the environment, identifies opportunities for improvement, gathers resources, and implements action to maximize those opportunities. The entrepreneur can be depicted as a role model in the community, a provider of employment opportunities for others, a stabilizing factor in society, and a primary contributor to the development of natural and human resources within a nation. Entrepreneurs provide new insights and perform a positive function in the economic development of a country. Entrepreneurs are those who are motivated to take risks, innovators, developer of new business ideas, and investor of money and other resources to establish enterprises that have growth potential.

The objectives of entrepreneurship education focus on: upgrading the social and economic status of self-employment as a career alternative, stimulating entrepreneurial attributes in young vocational trainees, facilitating the development of entrepreneurial ideas, and promoting the overall development of an "enterprise culture" in Nigeria. Entrepreneurship education is an area of study that can challenge trainees to adopt such an orientation to work.

Entrepreneurship is not just skills acquisition but it is an acquisition of skills, ideas geared towards creating employment for self and others. It leads to the

development of small scale, medium scale and large scale businesses based on creativity and innovation. Creativity is working within a disciplined mind, time and space to fashion out something that will fill the gap or solve human problems (Alex.I.I 2012). Innovation has to do with the persistent changes in pattern and acceptable forms. The successes of these businesses in building and developing our nation. The activities of these enterprises reduce poverty, increase rate of employment among youths. Through well-planned and executed entrepreneurship education, our youths will learn to be happy and fulfilled youths. They will also be productive, self-reliant and committed as employees or employers thereby allowing their unique abilities to be utilized for the development of community, local, state and national goals rather than abandoning their countries for greener pasture elsewhere.

Challenges of entrepreneurship education among youths in Nigeria.

The challenges of getting Nigerian Youths empowered to acquire skills and ideas necessary for creating employment, alleviating poverty, surmounting restiveness and most importantly reducing the rate of crime become a critical issue for the development of small, medium and large scale enterprises that later metamorphosed into national development. The first and foremost challenge confronting entrepreneurship education in Nigeria is poor curriculum implementation across tertiary institutions. The style of teaching entrepreneurship across the tertiary institutions in Nigeria has been flawed (Ifedili and Ofoegbu 2011). This, according to Garba (2004) has really impacted negatively on the

actualization of entrepreneurship goals among the Nigerian youths. Entrepreneurship Education is better imparted via industrial tours, professional talks from successful business owners and execution of business projects while in school. Other challenges include:

CORRUPTION: This vice has permeated the entire economic, political and social structure of Nigeria, has robbed the country of developing a vibrant economic base. Funds meant for development projects have been misappropriated, diverted, or embezzled and smuggled to foreign banks by our top officials in government, while some incompetent and corrupt bureaucrats and administrators in the public enterprises and parastatals have liquidated their organizations (Okafor, 2010).

MANAGEMENT INCOMPETENCIES: This is another major obstacle to the growth and development of entrepreneurship in Nigeria. It is very clear that the growing unemployment rate in Nigeria depicts that myriads of programmes established in Nigeria such as Nigeria Directorate of Employment (NDE) to tackle the menace of unemployment are yet to address the lapses in the university education. But if entrepreneurship education is incorporated into the curriculum of all the higher institutions in the country, these lapses will be systematically addressed.

***LACK OF TIME MANAGEMENT:** This emanates from inability to devote quality time for the building and development of our youths. This could be as a result of lackadaisical attitude on the side of the youths because of their erroneous perceptions that entrepreneurship is an elective or general course imposed on them by government just to increase their academic workloads (Ifedili and Ofoebgu 2011; Gabadeen and Raimi, 2012). But, however, time

is a critical factor essential for learning and understanding the basic principles such as the actual development of entrepreneurial skills, creative skills and innovative skills in individuals.

***LACK OF FUND:** This has raised a lot of dust in the field of entrepreneurship education. Adequate funds are needed for the successful implementation of educational curriculum. Besides, it is a fact attested by National University Commission (NUC) and National Board of Technical Education (NBTE). Lack of fund automatically dwindles the fate of would-be entrepreneur making him dependent rather than be independent and self-reliant. It equally robs the intending entrepreneur of his confidence and heightens his fears of failure in future.

***LACK OF INSTITUTIONALIZATION OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP VISION AND EDUCATIONAL**

MISSION: Entrepreneurship educators need capacity building to enable them use contents and teaching methodologies that would promote entrepreneurial mind-sets in students from various disciplines. Students need theory to support their practical learning experiences because practice makes perfect. We need to provide a conceptual background which allows students to learn and comprehend the in-thing in the real business world. We also need to pursue theory-driven agenda and expose young people to theoretical explanations of why some entrepreneurs succeed and some others fail.

*** FAMILY BACKGROUND:** Young people are often affected by their families, teachers and society as a whole. Important role models, such as parents and teachers, are often not very aware of the requirements and opportunities of entrepreneurship. This lack of

awareness results in a lack of encouragement for entrepreneurial activities, or even negative social attitudes that act as an obstacle to youth entrepreneurship (OECD, 2001). It is generally argued that education and training programmed not do enough to nurture entrepreneurial attitudes and skills, but rather prepare students for paid employment, despite some recent improvements in this area (Potter, 2008)

***MARKET BARRIERS ALSO AFFECT YOUTH ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION:** Financial markets may be biased away from supporting youth businesses. Youth-owned businesses may also face “discrimination” in product markets, with customers who can be skeptics about the reliability of their products or services. Similarly, due to limited resources, youth-owned firms are more likely to enter industries with low entry barriers where competition is fierce (OECD, 2001 in Oyelola O.T et al 2014).

The youth population is a heterogeneous one and there are some significant differences across groups in their potential for entrepreneurship and the barriers they face. Insufficient entrepreneurial skills to support desired productivity growth coupled with limited access to funding for private corporations and SMEs (including expensive capital), receive much of the blame. Similarly, some groups that face particularly strong labour market challenges include: ethnic minorities, those living in deprived areas, those from low income families, and those with low education levels. This suggests that care needs to be taken in assessing the particular barriers affecting different groups of young people. While there are some barriers and policy measures that are broadly the same for all

groups, there can also be a need to vary the scales and natures of support for different youth target groups.

In particular, a distinction can be made between disadvantaged youth – those who may be unemployed or inactive, live in a difficult environment or have major gaps in financial, human and network capital – and other young people who face less substantial obstacles but at the same time also represent an opportunity to increase entrepreneurship participation with appropriate policy intervention (Oyelola O.T et al 2014).

Conclusion and recommendation

Entrepreneurship education can be conceptualized as a specialized and all-round training programme designed by education authorities to change the worldview of students from job seekers to wealth creators by developing their latent talents and potentials. It is a learning directed towards developing in people those skills, competencies, understanding and attributes which equip them to be innovative and to identify, create, initiate and successfully start and manage personal /or community business and seek for opportunities to change society for the better while working for themselves or organization. Entrepreneurship occupies an important place in the process of economic development, as it has become a key concept in social and human discourse; it is considered a factor of economic and human development Abubakar(2010).It contributes in numerous ways towards creating new jobs, wealth creation, poverty reduction and income generation. But through well planned and executed entrepreneurship education, Oviawe (2010) observed, the Nigerian youths will learn to be happy and fulfilled, as they will be productive and committed as

employees or employers of labour. They will allow their unique abilities to be used for the development of the national and global goals rather than abandon their country for greener pastures. Hence, the provision of right skills to the youths to help them tackle the problem of unemployment and live a more prosperous life. Entrepreneurship Education enhances the ability, capability and potentials of individuals to understand risks for which economic benefits are assured Effort is needed to integrate entrepreneurship education into ongoing career preparation programs in secondary schools, Colleges education, Polytechnics and Universities, since it is important that the country's workforce have entrepreneurial attitudes before they enter employment, whether as employers or employees in order to compete effectively in the marketplace. Entrepreneurship

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education when effectively and efficiently implemented has the likelihood to precipitates self-employment among learners and accelerating sustainable growth and development. This is evident in a number of developed nations like Japan and America that utilized entrepreneurial (facilitative) education for improving their human capital as opposed to the traditional approach of teach-and-listen approach, which is prevalent in the developing third world nation (Witte and Wolf, 2003 ; Raimi et al., 2011). Finally, Nigeria as a nation must, therefore ensure that schools where youths are taught are deliberately planned to provide sector-specific skills needed for the development of human capital. This could be achieved by establishing base of capable professionals and entrepreneurs who will act as mentors.

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